

LUNAR UPPER MEGAREGOLITH DEPTH AS A CONSTRAINT ON THE BEGINNING OF RECORDED LUNAR HISTORY. A. M. Blevins¹, A. Rajsic¹ ¹Department of Earth, Environmental, and Planetary Sciences, Brown University, Providence, Rhode Island, 02912, USA (austin_blevins@brown.edu).

Introduction: The term “megaregolith” has come to describe the upper portion of the Moon’s crust [1-5]. The lunar megaregolith has been described to contain three distinct layers: The top layer is a meters-thick layer of fine material that has been heavily modified; the second layer is a km-thick layer composed of ejecta from impact events; and the lower layer is tens of km in depth and consists of bedrock fractured by impacts [5]. The top two layers are known as “upper megaregolith” [5] and can be thought of as the cumulative contribution of impact ejecta to the lunar crust. The exact thickness of the megaregolith has been modeled to be anywhere between 0.5 and 5 km [5,6]. However, Izquierdo et al. [4] found the thickness of the upper megaregolith should be between 3 and 5 km. This constraint can be used to model the lunar megaregolith under a variety of different chronology models. In particular, the starting age of the chronology can be varied. This has implications for the time of melt sheet cooling [7] and the age of the South Pole Aitken (SPA) basin [8,9].

Modeling Megaregolith with CTEM: The formation of megaregolith is modeled using the Cratered Terrain Evolution Model (CTEM). CTEM is a Monte Carlo impact bombardment model that allows for rapid emplacement of thousands of craters and calculation of each crater’s properties, such as ejecta blanket [10-12]. Ejecta is calculated based on a modified version of the Maxwell Z-model [10], where ejecta thickness is calculated as a function of distance from the crater center using a paraboloid shell model [13,14].

To emplace craters that represent the lunar basins (>200 km in diameter [15]), CTEM’s “Quasi-Monte Carlo” (QuasiMC) mode is utilized. QuasiMC allows for the emplacement of manually-defined basins alongside random craters (<200 km in diameter) emplaced with the Monte Carlo method [16,17]. The basin sequence of Blevins et al. [17] is utilized. This is a plausible sequence constructed from syncretizing three other sequences [15,18,19]. The rest of the craters are emplaced according to the Monte Carlo method, using the Neukum production and chronology function [20].

The Role of Crater Interiors in Megaregolith Generation: Both simple and complex (including peak-ring and multiring basins) contain a breccia lens that forms during the impact process [5]. For smaller craters, this breccia lens contributes to regolith production [21], but for larger craters it contributes to megaregolith production [5]. As much as

60% of megaregolith contribution may come from breccia lenses [5].

The version of CTEM used for this project does not currently have a robust model for breccia lens generation. Richardson and Abramov [5] use a model for the breccia lens that scales with crater size. This model will be incorporated into this version of CTEM, and the role of breccia lenses in the generation of megaregolith will be further constrained through numerous CTEM simulations.

Figure 1 shows the megaregolith thickness for the lower limit (no breccia lens) and upper limit (entire crater interior contains breccia lens of maximum possible thickness) of breccia lens generation. The true thickness should fall somewhere between these extremes. Once the breccia lens model is implemented, the megaregolith depth can be compared under different chronologies.

Figure 1: Results of a 4.3 Gyr QuasiMC simulation using no breccia lens (left) and overestimated breccia lens (right). The top image is the megaregolith thickness map, while the bottom image is the histogram of megaregolith thickness in the style of Richardson and Abramov [5]. For the lower limit, there are too many pixels with little megaregolith thickness, which correspond to crater interiors. For the upper limit, the breccia lens is too thick in crater interiors, resulting in an overestimation of overall megaregolith thickness.

Preliminary Indications: Figure 2 shows the megaregolith thickness for four pure Monte Carlo simulations, each with a different starting point. The megaregolith is thicker throughout the Moon with longer time for more craters to accumulate.

Figure 2: Megaregolith thickness for pure Monte Carlo runs that lasted 4.31 Ga (top left), 4.35 Ga (top right), 4.40 Ga (bottom left), and 4.45 Ga (bottom right). These values are lower limits as the breccia lens model for crater interiors has not yet been implemented (see above).

This figure demonstrates the approach that will be taken with the completed model. Different starting times will be used to see which are matches for the 3-5 km upper megaregolith depth observed by Izquierdo et al. [4]. The agreeable start times can thus be estimates for the beginning of recorded lunar chronology. If one assumes that the South Pole-Aitken basin formed immediately after this start time [8,9], the age found from this work can be used to predict the age of the basin. This prediction can then be tested by the upcoming Artemis missions to the lunar South Pole, which have an objective of returning materials from the South Pole-Aitken basin to Earth so they can be radiometrically dated, giving the age of the impact [9].

Modeling Megaregolith with Cratermaker:

The CTEM simulations are confined to a square gridspace, which results in several inaccuracies, particularly with the position of basins relative to each other. The next generation of cratered terrain evolution model is Cratermaker, which works in a fully three dimensional grid [22]. Fig. 3 shows a pure Monte Carlo test run in Cratermaker. Running these simulations with a validated Cratermaker would result in a megaregolith thickness model with fewer assumptions.

Figure 1: Monte Carlo simulation of total ejecta thickness in meters (which is a proxy for upper megaregolith depth) in Cratermaker, run for 4.3 Gyr. This is a proof-of-concept run and results are not indicative of true upper megaregolith depth.

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